

ARTIFICIAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND AUTONOMOUS ROBOTS

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Sam KODO is from Togo , he has over 15 years of experience in Robotic , He build his Robots using only e-wastes .

He is entirely a Self taught and started learning robotics when he was just 8 years old .

Sam is the Founder of Infinite Loop , his company produces Low cost computers powered by Solar energy and 3D Games.

He is also Volunteers in many community programs where he teaches youth how to build their own robots and to program them .

Abstract

In this article we will try to answer a question through simple experiments in order to test the hypothesis as to whether one day a robot can become autonomous to one day take control¹ of humanity.

¹ Capek , Carel

RUR : Russum ' s Universal Robot , the difference , 2011

Tolbiac Rez-de-jardin –magazin [2011-31482]

We define an autonomous Robot, a machine capable of making decisions by oneself without human intervention, thanks to its program that it embeds in its memory and the aid of its sensors allowing it to acquire the information coming from the outside world such as light, color, shape, sounds, distance .

FIG.1 ROBERT.1

For our study we have constructed a humanoid care robot which we named ROBERT.1 in FIG. 1, it is equipped with wheels to move on a flat surface, arms to grasp an object, a color sensor to distinguish many colors and a Micro controller Arduino Uno.

In the first experiment as in the following figure, we wrote a program allowing the robot to detect a cube of green color.

A green cube should symbolize a sick person to rescue, so every time the Robot detected the green cube and grabbed it by dropping it into a basket, he was rewarded with a 3 point of bonus. Each 3 point bonus unlocked a variable that would allow the Robot to accelerate a little faster in its movements.

From the beginning of the experiment everything worked as expected, the robot went straight to the green cube and placed it in the basket in the X, Y, Z coordinates that were stored in his memory.

We then decided to repeat the experiment, this time allowing the Robot to detect two cubes of different colors.

The green cube should symbolize a patient to rescue and have 3 bonus points that should allow the robot to improve his speed, and a yellow cube that should symbolize his meal which should be worth 5 bonus points which should allow the robot to also improve its speed.

Once the robot has a total bonus of 10 points or more, his mission should end and reset his variable to 0 to resume his mission.

At the beginning of the second experiment, two yellow cubes and two green cubes were placed and the Robot was started.

From the start, ROBERT.1 advanced only to the two yellow cubes that symbolized the meals and placed them in basket A, once the total bonus of 10 points was obtained, ROBERT.1 reset its variable and took care of the last two remaining cubes.

This study demonstrates that although ROBERT.1 was autonomous in his ability to judge and analyze the information he lacked common sense and morality.

In the second experiment, the yellow cube, which represented a higher bonus point than the green, was his first priority, whereas in the first experiment the robot had only one mission to save the sick which was the green cubes.

Most of our robots we have in our homes, factories are not different from ROBERT.1 in our first experience, because most of them act to help us or even take care for us.

In the second experiment, we gave ROBERT.1 a survival instinct by allowing him to feed by detecting the yellow-colored cubes and we observed a change in his behavior, ROBERT.1 which was previously intended to save lives begins to think about his own survival and to act in his own interests.

We then decided to program ROBERT.1 in order to detect three colors: Green which means a sick person to rescue who is worth a 3 point bonus, yellow representing his meal worth a 5 point bonus and finally Red as in the following figure which represents an enemy which, once detected, subtracts a bonus of -5 points.

We also have a second basket B placed at a coordinate X, Y, Z differ from the first.

We decide to place on its course, 1 cube of color green, 1 cube of color Yellow and 4 cubes of yellow colors.

From the start, we found that ROBERT.1 first attempted to grab all 4 red-colored cubes by placing them in basket B, then moved to the yellow cube and finally the green cube by placing them in the basket A.

This experience allows us to understand that ROBERT.1 did not hesitate to eliminate all his enemies symbolizing the red color which could hinder him, we could equip ROBERT.1 of a Laser to destroy the red cubes to make the experience more Interesting but we did not continue the experience.

It is enough to note that the behavior of a machine can be modified by endowing it with an instinct of survival, this survival instinct can be its capacity to recharge itself or anything else that can reward the machine for the purpose to make it evolve.

ROBERT.1 in the third experiment acts as any animal would seek to feed itself, the question that remains as to whether a Robot can take control of humanity one day will depend on the intention of the programmer or the designer and the respect of the laws set forth by the famous science fiction author Isaac Asimov ²through his book "Runaround", published in 1942, containing the famous three laws of robotics that every robotic engineer must respect for the survival of mankind:

- A robot may not injure a human being or, through inaction, allow a human being to come to harm.
- A robot must obey the orders given it by human beings except where such orders would conflict with the First Law.
- A robot must protect its own existence as long as such protection does not conflict with the First or Second Laws.

² Asimov , Isaac
Les Robots , j'ai lu , 2012